

Does Scarcity Work in the Hospitality Business?

Introduction -

Demand and supply are two important factors in business . These two factors are linked with each other . If demand goes high and supply is low the prices go up ; however, if supply is high and demand is low, prices can easily plummet . This is a classic business theory however , it doesn't apply to every business for example , Hospitality industry . In hospitality business , pricing and demand are not always logical - emotions , timings and availability often affect decisions . After the Internet revolution the buying patterns of individuals have changed in hospitality business .

The aim of this research is to find out , “Does Scarcity Work in the Hospitality Business ? ” . This paper could help the hospitality business to increase revenue during peak booking seasons .

Literature review -

In the year 1991 , a book by Robert Cialdini , ” Influence” mentioned that scarcity is one of the 6 universal persuasion

principles . This is why we see “limited time offer ” or “only 10 pieces are present in the world ”. This makes an individual perceive goods as more exclusive and this creates a psychological barrier called the fear of missing out .

Scarcity is not a term only for exclusivity in goods ; it can also affect your brain while thinking as found in Mullainathan & Shafir research . They found that it can affect our cognitive capacity (bandwidth) , attention , create a tunneling effect and also lead to cognitive stress .

The latest research by Hamilton et al. He found that scarcity has types :

- 1.) Product Scarcity - when a product is limited (low production high demand)
- 2.) Resource Scarcity - when consumers have less money or time to make a purchase.

When scarcity effect an individuals , it has a mechanism given by Lynn (1991) known as Meta - analysis of Scarcity . He proposed that scarcity creates a psychological pressure that

changes consumer behavior. The product desirability increases .

Mechanism Proposed -

1.) Reactance (Psychological Resistance to loss of Freedom)

When consumer perceive their freedom of choice is restricted (only few rooms are left). They feel psychological reactance .

This reactance increases motivation to acquire the scarce good , because buying it restores freedom .

2.) Commodity theory

Scarce goods are seen as more valuable simply because they are less available.

People infer that if something is scarce, it must be desirable, socially valued, or high quality.

3.) Social Proof & Competition

Scarcity due to *high demand* signals popularity

This social validation makes consumers want it more.

4.) Signaling and Status

Owning scarce items can be a signal of status, uniqueness, or insider knowledge (Louis vuitton, Birkin bag, Chanel , Gucci)

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Methodology

This research was conducted using two main sources of data :

- 1.) Survey that represented booking conditions .
- 2.) Offline records from a real family run homestay situated in Shimla , Himachal Pradesh , India .

The goal of this dual- method approach is to find out that how does scarcity works in both online and offline hospitality Business and real-life situations change the customer behavior

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1.) Survey data

A short survey was conducted among 30 participants of different nationalities , including Indians , British, filipinos ,

and The USA. This survey aimed to understand how does people react to scarcity signals while booking a room online .

The survey consisted of six main questions , consisting of multiple choice and small response questions . These questions were asked to understand what are the factors affecting hotel booking .

This survey was conducted in person and by use of google forms . The participants were asked to the imagine themselves when they are booking rooms online . Their responses are organized and analyzed in Apple Numbers .

2.) Offline Booking data

This data was taken to understand the real behavior of individuals . This data was recored in offline booking register of the researcher's family homestay . The homestay have 4 rooms and these rooms are mostly booked in peak seasons (winter and summers) . The offline data consists of booking dates , prices and room availability.

The observation showed that during peak seasons scarcity was the main factor of booking - when the consumer knew that only 2 rooms are left , the consumer booked the room at a high price . This is a real world evidence that scarcity influences more emotional where host behavior , aesthetic , scent etc makes scarcity more effective .

3.) Comparison approach

The two data sets are juxtaposed on the basis of qualitatively to identify behavioral differences between online and offline booking situation . The analysis mainly focus on understanding how digital and physical situations can change the effectiveness of scarcity principle .

Results

1.) Survey results :

In the survey 30 participants took part in the survey , including respondents from India, the United Kingdom, the Philippines , and the USA . The main goal as to understand whether scarcity cues can manipulate customer's choices an online environment .

Figure 1

Out of 30 responses , only one participant selected the scarcity message “only two rooms left ” . The remaining individuals preferred comfort - or trust- based options like “Comfortable stay available.”

When asked what factor s mattered most hen booking a room , the majority selected comfort , price and reviews . Only a small number chose limited availability as their top priority . In the question about freebies most participants choose Yes or Maybe (figure 1), showing that small rewards could encourage repeat booking — this supports the principle of reciprocity.

There was question about feeling pressure when booking a room offline , the majority of people choose Yes or No (fig2), elucidating the theory of Bandwidth .

Figure 2

A question asked the participants “Did they ever felt regret after booking due to urgency or scarcity ?” The majority of people respond YES. This finding suggests that although scarcity cues might not strongly influence people to book , they can still create post - decision regret (figure 3) when individuals feel they acted too quickly or under pressure.

Figure 3

These results shows , that scarcity had minimal influence in the survey, suggesting that when people are calm and have time to compare different options on the website . Hence scarcity cues do not strongly affect their decisions .

2.) Offline Booking results :

Data is taken from a homestay booking register which revealed a contrasting pattern . During peak seasons (summer & winter) , scarcity worked effectively .

When guests were told that only 1 room or 2 rooms were left . They tend to book the room immediately, even when prices were higher than usual . Records shows that the rooms with scenic views were constantly booked , despite being more expensive .

During off - season periods. Guests negotiated prices more and took longer to make decisions which demonstrates scarcity was less effective when availability was high .

This finding suggests that emotional and situational factors boosts booking . For example - fatigue after travel , the smell of premises , desire of comfort , in-person trust with the host and visible limitations of rooms . As result , the power of booking of scarcity increased in offline conditions .

Discussion :

The results actively demonstrate that scarcity doesn't always influence consumer behavior in the same way across different hospitality settings .

In the survey (online context) , most of the participants didn't choose scarcity cues such as "Only two rooms left " Instead , they preferred options emphasizing comfort , price or reviews . This indicates that people have more time to think rationally rather than outdoor factors such as fatigue after travel etc .

However , in the offline booking context , scarcity appeared to be a strong motivator. Guests booked rooms when told about limited rooms were left , even at higher pricing . This suggests that scarcity works better in emotional , real world conditions

where people experience urgency , physical fatigue , and trust-based interactions with the host .

This difference between online and offline behavior supports the psychological theory of cognitive bandwidth proposed by Mullainathan and shafir . This theory explains people when they are mentally or emotionally tired , they are more likely to make impulsive decisions because capacity of mind processing information gets slower . In case of travelers , scarcity cues like “only two rooms left ” may have felt more real and urgent due to exhaustion or travel stress .

On the other hand, in online situations , scarcely cues may be seen as marketing tactics rather than a genuine shortage . This resonates with Lynn (1991) - Meta - analysis of Scarcity which suggests that scarcity loses its charm if consumers suspects manipulation . In addition, CIALDINI - Influence book explains that scarcity works best when people believe the opportunity is authentic and unique - which is a limitation of online setting .

Another important observation is the emotional response of regret . 52% of the individuals felt a sense of regret after impulsive booking . This shows that scarcity can also manipulate actions as well as emotion as suggested by Hamilton et al. (2019) . Scarcity creates psychological tension , sometimes leading to regret . This finding contributes to understating the emotional cost of scarcity- based marketing .

Overall, the findings support that scarcity isn't a universal coaxing tool - its effectiveness depends on the context , emotion , and credibility of the situation. For hospitality businesses , this means that using scarcity may be effective in physical interactions but less effective in digital marketing unless backed by authenticity .

Conclusion:

This study explored whether scarcity works effectively in hospitality business by comparing online and offline booking behaviors . The results revealed that scarcity cues such as “Only two rooms left ,” had minimal influence on participants in the online survey but it worked strongly in offline settings .

These findings suggest that scarcity is more effective when consumers are in emotionally and physically engaging environments, such as during in-person booking, where urgency and limited availability felt more authentic. In contrast, online users, have more time & options to compare, and often rely on comfort, price, and reviews instead.

This research highlights that context matters - scarcity can't be treated as a one-size-fits-all marketing tool. For hospitality business, it's most effective when used sincerely and combined with genuine value and positive customer experiences.

Future studies could examine how digital booking platforms can recreate emotional engagement of offline interactions to make scarcity more believable and less manipulative.

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